

LEGAL CONSEQUENCES ARISING FROM SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN GAFUR GHULAM'S WORK.

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Annotation: The solutions to the problems in Ghafur Ghulam's works, the achievements and shortcomings of the 20th century fiction, the legal solutions to the stories, the presentation of gender equality issues.

Key words: Short story, law, law, artistic analysis, heroes of the work, crime, solution, children's rights, role of women.

The rare talent, philosopher, poet, prose writer Ghafur Ghulam was a people's writer who was able to listen to the hearts of our people and all well-intentioned humanity and felt their pain from the heart. Most of Ghafur Ghulam's creative activity consists of prose works, especially stories, short stories. Studying these short stories and stories from the point of view of the period and the interpretation of the person is important for the education of youth, the formation of their attitude to the cultural heritage, the fiction literature of the 20th century. How important it is to learn new thinking and skills, Because we have not yet explored the great heritage left by our ancestors. Ghafur Ghulam directly through the works "Yigit", "Ko'ngilsizning qilig'i", "Kim aybdor", "Mening o'g'rigina bolam", "Afandi o'lmydigan bo'ldi", "Chorbazarchi" He was able to show the existing shortcomings of the 20th century and the image of the era. The story that we will analyze first is "Chorbazarchi". Through this short story, Ghafur Ghulam, we can see that in the 20th century, our people were engaged in various professions, because we can also witness that it was affected by the negative aspects of the social environment of that time. Ahmed Sedov explained that another notable cooperative took over all trade and the market, and as a result, residents were forced to engage in various professions. It would be appropriate to analyze this episode, that is, some crimes are shown here. The first of these is the crime of theft. That is, Ahmad Sedov was engaged in many professions, and at the end he also became a thief. Article 169 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes theft, and we can qualify this situation according to this article.

In Ghafur Ghulam's story "Mening o'g'rigina bolam", this is the most important thing. It is also stated that many families in the 20th century lived in poverty and children became orphans as a result of the war. The young thief explains that he mainly rejects this profession, and mentions that there is only one reason to start this job, that is, the lack of money in the family and the fact that there is nothing left at home to feed and educate the children. We should pay attention to this in the story, which is also noteworthy from an ethnographic point of view. Because through this work, a whole house and the whole society opposite to it are described.

He described a wonderful situation of our people through the story "Yigit". showed that even during Ghafur Ghulam's time, humanity began to study the culture of other peoples along with national traditions. This situation is described by the poet as a young man standing at the box office, and the description of many people waiting in line to enter the cinema showed that our people's worldview is expanding, love for cinema and theater has awakened.

Our poet wanted to reveal that all people living in the society are equal before the law, regardless of their language, religion, social origin, through the story "Cho'tir xotinning toleyi". This situation is stated in Article 58 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Women and men have equal rights". Now, if we look directly at the events in the story, one village had to hand over the specified amount of cotton to the government. After that, women also start working and hand over the specified amount in excess, and men are surprised by the courage shown by women in practice, they understand that getting women to work and work helps the development of society and the performance of the functions of the state. The development of events begins in this way: in the morning, the husband does not see his wife with him, and he is very surprised by this. When he went out into the street, he saw that the wife of the collective farmer was not at home, the women had left their homes. Then a man says that all the women are working in the fields, and when he goes and looks, the women are planting fertilizers on the ground.

After that, there was a lot of harvest, and the whole village and the government were happy about it. In each of his stories, our poet tried to bring to our readers the situations that afflict the society. Analyzing the next story, this story attracts the reader like other stories. The social situation and neighborly relations of a poor family and a rich family were highlighted in the short story "Ko'ngilsizning qilig'i". There is a young girl named Sarvaroy, and her father is described as very poor, while Sarvaroy is also said to be 17 years old, and her brothers are not yet

circumcised. In the story, mainly poverty causes various negative consequences. The first of these is that Sarvaroy was forced to go and serve in Kasimboy's household. The second case can be seen when a rich man comes to his neighbor's house and illegally occupies one apartment alone. Another important aspect is that Kasimboy's son, Ganibayvachcha, forces and tricks the girl. I can see this situation in accordance with Article 41 of the Code of Administrative Responsibility, which also establishes responsibility for fraud. Of course, the examples given are in the current legal system and legislation. We do not know what liability would have created under the previous legal system. Another important aspect is that Sarvaroy was given in marriage at the age of 17. If we compare this with the legal system of the 21st century, Article 15 of the Family Code stipulates that the age of marriage is 18 years, but it is a forced marriage of a girl, that is, Sarvaroy. Now, if we consider it with the norms established in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in Article 136 of the Criminal Code, forcing a woman to touch the ground causes the following legal consequences: "a fine of up to twenty-five times the amount of the basic calculation or up to three hundred and sixty hours of compulsory community service or shall be punished by correctional work for up to three years, or restriction of liberty from one to three years, or deprivation of liberty for up to three years."

Ghafur Ghulam's short story "Kim aybdor" reveals the general situation of some uneducated and inexperienced people living in the society and their stupidity, and along with this, our poet showed that the state is making progress in social spheres. That is, as soon as Madmisa got on the train, unfortunate events began to happen, the first of which was that Madmisa unknowingly stepped on the handle of the train, and as a result, the train stopped. And then Madmisa was in Moscow, in this huge city he was very surprised and confused, he saw huge buildings, and he was following her friend, and finally after much trouble, Madmisa found her friend's address, but the development of events was not over yet, as Madmisa had just seen the taxi for the first time. And after that he got into another surprising situation. This situation was shundy, he had never seen and used an elevator in his life. As a result, he did not know how to press the elevator button, and when he unexpectedly pressed it, the elevator broke down and Madmisa herself was trapped inside.

The beginning of the story "Afandi o'lmaydigan bo'ldi" began with a very interesting incident. Efendi collected firewood from the field with a donkey and sold it. And the money he won was three soums. The structure of this coin was very unusual. Nasriddin Afandi lost this coin while traveling, and as a result, he

began to illegally embezzle money and other valuables from all those who passed through this desert, and this process continued for more than 5 years. Let's compare this situation with the legal system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Article 166 of the Criminal Code is robbery, that is, open robbery of someone else's property. They can be prosecuted with the use of sanctions in the prescribed manner. Through this work, Ghafur Ghulam wanted to convey the existence of various robbery groups that existed in the 20th century. At the same time, the main character of the story mentions that the income of the population is not enough to buy consumer goods.

During the time when Ghafur Ghulam lived, it was very difficult to live and live, there was almost no opportunity even to create freely, but the famous poet paid all his attention to the pain of the people and its future. Let's take just one example, if you ask who is the one who portrayed the useless young man in the story "Tirilgan Murda" at the level of a perfect human being, then of course this person was Ghafur Ghulam, another noteworthy aspect of the story. that is, special attention was paid to the issue of gender equality. In other words, Mamadjon's wife was both knowledgeable and hard-working, which will cover the shortcomings in her life. Not everyone can create such an image. Such works are performed only by poets who have a deep place in the hearts of the people. In addition, ethnographic situations are described in the stories and anecdotes listed above. The educational system of the 20th century highlighted the fact that production is low and the general consumption of the population is decreasing day by day. In addition, I think that the purpose of highlighting the fact that women poets are the most important point of society in many of his works is to prevent their discrimination and to build a legal, democratic state with equal rights of representatives of every category in society. and showed that he should use the opportunities.

References:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan
2. Code of Administrative Responsibility
3. Criminal Code
4. Labor Code
5. Selected works Gafur Ghulam

